

In vivo T1-mapping using Open-MOLLI in GE scanners

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INTRODUCTION:

Standardization of quantitative measuring approaches in MR is crucial to provide reproducible measurements that can be reliably used in the clinic to distinguish healthy from pathological tissues [1-3]. However, the implementation of techniques such as T1 mapping is known to vary between vendors, and even when the same family of sequences is used, small differences in the timings, amplitudes and shapes of gradient and RF pulses change the impact of confounding mechanisms (e.g., magnetization transfer effects) affecting reproducibility and hindering the method's applicability for clinical diagnostic and follow up. Precise pulse sequence matching across centers and vendors has been shown to improve reproducibility, either using vendor-specific pulse sequence development tools [4], or applying vendor-agnostic frameworks such as VENUS [1] or Pulseq [5].

The open-source myocardial T1 mapping (Open-MOLLI) sequence [6,7] was previously developed to enable reproducible cardiac T1-mapping. Open-MOLLI has since been tested in different Siemens systems (1.5 T and 3.0T) and compared to the vendor MOLLI implementations and was shown to provide comparable myocardial T1 values with equivalent same-scan repeatability [8]. In this work, we extend the Open-MOLLI method and adapt the sequence to comply with specific GE requirements, demonstrating its feasibility to be run also on GE systems.

METHODS:

MOLLI consists of an inversion-recovery (IR) sequence with a balanced steady-state free precession (bSSFP) readout and quantitative T1 parameter estimation (T1 mapping) (see

Figure 1). Open-MOLLI uses the same IR strategy as MOLLI with the trigger scheme 5(3)3. It is publicly available at <https://github.com/asgaspar/OpenMOLLI>. Open-MOLLI was adapted for the GE system using TOPPE [9] by labelling the sequence into 4 blocks: the inversion pulse, the readout, the delay between readouts and the delay between inversion. The Inversion pulse was adapted to the system by reducing the B1 peak value.

The GE implementation of Open-MOLLI was tested by carrying out T1 brain mapping in 2 healthy subjects (both male) using a 3T Signa PET-MR scanner equipped with a 32 channel Nova Medical Head Coil.

The acquisition was performed in one axial slice of the brain, and the mean T1 was estimated in white (WM) and grey matter (GM) manually delineated regions of interest. Open-MOLLI was acquired with an undersampling factor of 2, including 24 autocalibration lines in the center of k-space, the following parameters were used: field-of-view of 354 × 327 mm², matrix size 256×144 (reconstructed to 256×218), slice thickness of 8 mm, TR/TE=3.24/3.12 ms, flip angle of 35°, readout bandwidth 808 Hz/pixel, with initial (and shortest) inversion time (TI) of 183 ms. The sequence timing was built according to a (simulated) heart rate of 60 bpm.

The data were reconstructed offline using GRAPPA, and magnitude signals were used for T1 estimation in Matlab. A 3-parameter analytic model $\text{Signal}(A,B,T1^*)=|A-B*\exp(-TI/T1^*)|$ with correction of $T1 = (B/A-1)T1^*$ was used for T1 estimation[3].

RESULTS:

Open-MOLLI was successfully implemented in the GE system. Figure 2a presents the T1-weighted images obtained for the first TI in the two subjects. Figure 2b shows the respective T1 maps estimated for each subject.

The mean T1 values for each region of interest are presented in Table 1, along with their standard deviations and the respective T1 literature values for GM and WM at 3.0T. The mean T1 over the two subjects was 772±22 ms for WM, and 1244±72 ms for GM, which is in agreement with the literature ($T1^{\text{WM}}=860$ ms and $T1^{\text{GM}}=1200$ ms)[10-13].

DISCUSSION:

The work presented a proof-of-concept of the applicability of Open-MOLLI in a different vendor (GE) from that in which it was originally implemented (Siemens). We were able to estimate T1 values for the brain (GM and WM) that are consistent with those reported in the literature at 3.0T. The adaptation of the Open-MOLLI T1-mapping sequence to the GE system required changes in the sequence that remain compatible with previously used Siemens systems. The current GE Open-MOLLI implementation still lacks the cardiac-triggering

capabilities required for myocardial T1-mapping, which will be implemented in the near future. This will be followed by a comprehensive multi-centric evaluation of the repeatability (within-session) and reproducibility (across scanners) of the measured cardiac T1 values, including a comparison with equivalent vendor MOLLI-like measurements.

CONCLUSION:

This work demonstrates the feasibility of applying Open-MOLLI in GE systems, paving the way for future inter-scanner reproducibility studies.

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Figures

Figure 1: MR pulse sequence diagram of Open-MOLLI applied in GE system. The inversion pulse was scaled and the labels were defined for four segments: inversion pulse, readout, delay between readout and delay between inversions.

Table 1: Mean T1 (in ms) values over white matter and grey matter region of interest represented in Figure 1.

	Open-MOLLI		Literature ¹⁰
	Subject 1	Subject 2	
White matter	788±92	757±70	860
Grey matter	1193±97	1295±116	1200

Figure 2: (A) T1-weighted images obtained with Open-MOLLI for two healthy subjects. Inversion times (TI) for each image was 183 ms, and respective (B) T1 maps (in ms) for both sequences. Region of interest for white matter (white) and grey matter (black) are represented, with respective mean T1 and standard deviation.